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**Towards FAIR Research Data Management in Experimental
Materials Science: A Metadata Pipeline**

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Science is a collective and cooperative endeavour and has always relied on the communication of results and discoveries among scientists. However, in contemporary science, communication is compromised by an academic culture that pressures researchers to continuously publish (the so called ‘publish or perish’ culture) and by an emphasis on journal articles writing which eventually undermines the sharing of other worthy scientific products such as datasets and models. In the long run, this academic culture creates problems for the tenability of scientific results. Indeed, in the last decades, we have witnessed the emergence of phenomena that undermine scientific credibility, such as questionable research practices and a pervasive failure to reproduce results in many fields, such as biomedicine and behavioural sciences (the so-called ‘reproducibility crisis’).

The Open Science movement emerged as a solution to these problems, promoting a series of practices to increase the transparency and, ultimately, the quality and reproducibility of scientific research. One prominent practice is research data management according to the so-called FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Despite their widespread uptake, especially in the life sciences, applying the FAIR principles, i.e., FAIRification, is challenging and puzzling.

This thesis describes a FAIRification project undertaken during my internship at the National Metrology Institute of Italy (INRiM). My project focused mostly on metadata management, interoperability, and the use of electronic laboratory notebooks (ELNs). The aim of the work was mainly exploratory. The main result is a metadata pipeline for a specific experiment in materials science, namely the Spin-Orbit Torque (SOT) measurement in the field of spintronics. The metadata pipeline transfers metadata from the experimental context of the data production until their publication in a domain-specific repository, in a FAIR way.

In Chapter 2, I will give some background necessary to understand the project. First, I will explain the main points of Open Science, the concept of machine-actionability, the FAIR principles, and I will give a brief overview of FAIRification frameworks. Then, I will describe the context of the project, the setup of the SOT measurement at INRiM, which is controlled by a Python program, and the difficulties of FAIRification for experimental materials science. Finally, I will make a brief comparison between a traditional data science

project and a FAIRification project, which aims to build an infrastructure to enable data science.

In Chapter 3, I will explain the methodology and the tools used to build the metadata pipeline. The methodology is contextual FAIRification, which adapts the FAIRification process to the scientific context at hand and suggests the choice of a particular focus. In our case, the focus was metadata and interoperability. In Chapter 3, I will also discuss the tools used to build the metadata pipeline, which are three. The first tool is CHADA, a metadata standard for material characterization (Comité Européen de Normalisation, 2021). The second tool is an electronic laboratory notebook (ELN) software, eLabFTW (CARPi et al., 2017). The third tool is NOMAD, an open-source platform for materials science data (Scheidgen et al., 2023).

In Chapter 4, I will describe in detail the main result of the thesis, namely the metadata pipeline. I will first give an overview of the pipeline and successively describe each step. The pipeline starts from the definition of a flat conceptual metadata schema, i.e., a list of keys written according to the CHADA. This metadata standard is used to build a template in the chosen ELN software, eLabFTW. Successively, an API integration between the Python program controlling the instruments in the laboratory where the measurement is performed and eLabFTW creates an experiment entry in eLabFTW containing the metadata coming from the original Python program. Finally, the metadata were prepared for publication in a FAIR and interoperable way using NOMAD, which allows dataset publication with DOIs and ensures interoperability through its schema language, NOMAD Metainfo. To create a suitable schema, the keys from the flat conceptual metadata schema were matched with the NOMAD Metainfo. Then, API integration enabled automatic data transfer from eLabFTW to NOMAD. Finally, we reached only partial interoperability of the metadata of the SOT measurement – mostly due to the scarce population of NOMAD Metainfo.

In Chapter 5, I will recap the project and reflect on the limitations of the work and on future prospects for FAIRification in experimental materials science.

Chapter 2

Open Science and FAIR Principles: From Theory to Practice

The Open Science movement started from bottom-up practices, and its ideas have been increasingly adopted by many institutions, at the national (Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca, 2022), European (European Commission, n.d.), and global levels (UNESCO, 2021). Despite this proliferation of initiatives, practices and institutional policies, the understanding of openness is not always clear, as it may refer to many concepts such as transparency, sharing, pluralism and so on. For now, we will use Open Science as an umbrella term. The ideas of Open Science do not only refer to scientific publications, but also to other scientific objects such as data and algorithms. Indeed, one of the most prominent practices of Open Science is FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) research data management. Yet, the FAIR principles are rather abstract in their formulation and applying them to real-life scenarios (FAIRification) is challenging.

The project undertaken in this thesis aims to put into practice FAIR data management in the context of the National Metrology Institute of Italy (INRiM). The INRiM has two main missions: the first one is carrying out scientific research in metrology, the science of measurement (broadly construed), and materials science, while the second one is creating and maintaining the national standards for units of measurement. The FAIRification project presented in this thesis focuses on research metadata, specifically in materials science, in the field of spintronics.

Before going into the details of the envisioned FAIRification project, which will be discussed in Chapter 3 and 4, in this chapter I will give some coordinates to understand the background of such work, by defining important concepts and by describing the context in which this project is situated.

Here is the plan for this chapter. First, I will analyse the conceptual background (§2.1). I will start from a brief illustration of the concepts of Open Science and openness (§2.1.1). I will proceed by describing the concept of machine-actionability (§2.1.2) and by examining the FAIR principles (§2.1.3). Then I will briefly delineate the main frameworks for FAIRification (§2.1.4).

Second, I will describe the context of our FAIRification project (§2.2). Namely, I will analyse the difficulties of FAIRification in the context of materials science (§2.2.1) and the experimental setup of the specific measurement we took as a case study (§2.2.2)

Third, I will contrast FAIRification with a traditional data science project and show how a FAIRification process can be understood as the building blocks of an infrastructure enabling and supporting data science and machine learning (§2.3).

2.1 Conceptual Background

2.1.1 Open Science

Even though secrecy has always played a role in the history of science (for example, Kepler did not get full access to Tycho Brahe’s astronomical data until Brahe’s death), according to a rather popular picture, science has always been open (Resnik, 2023). Indeed, the sociologist of science Robert Merton (1973) includes communalism within the ethos of science, which is the set of values and norms guiding and constraining the practices of the scientists. According to the norm of communalism, scientific results are part of a “common heritage” (p. 273), and thus scientists should communicate fully and openly their findings and acknowledge to be a part of a communal enterprise which stands ‘on the shoulders of giants’.

Despite the importance of openness in the history of science, the idea of Open Science and the Open Science movement is a rather new phenomenon, which is often understood as a response to a set of problems emerging from contemporary scientific communication and dissemination, as the philosopher Sabina Leonelli (2023, Ch.2) explains. Indeed, contemporary scientific research is dominated by the production and publication of a high number of journal articles. Even though the labour of authors, reviewers, and editors of scientific journals is supported by public funding, the articles are actually available only to those institutions which can afford high subscription fees. This system results in high-profit margins for publishing companies. Moreover, the focus on articles undermines the dissemination of other arguably important components of scientific research, such as data, metadata, models, software and algorithms, which usually have a limited circulation.

Furthermore, the emphasis on publication in prestigious journals and on gaining funding pressures scientists into overstating their results and embracing questionable research practices (such as p-hacking and cherry-picking). Thus, the trustworthiness of science seems to be eroded by this culture. One example is the so-called ‘reproducibility crisis’ (Fidler and Wilcox, 2021), whose main manifestation is the failure to reproduce many

experimental results in several fields within biomedicine and behavioural sciences. In sum, the worry is that the contemporary dissemination of scientific research, characterized by a high level of competitiveness and commodification, dangerously hinders science itself.

The Open Science movement emerged to tackle these problems. The main idea is that endorsing and facilitating the sharing of scientific products (from journal articles to datasets) will improve transparency, and hence the collective scrutiny of results, and ultimately improve the quality (including reproducibility) and inclusivity of scientific research (Leonelli, 2023, p.19).

But what exactly do we mean by open? The jurist Ludovica Paseri (2024, Ch.2) unpacks the idea of ‘openness’ of Open Science in three understandings, which loosely relate to the historical development of the movement. The first one is openness as *democratization*, characterising the ‘open access’ movement (2000s), a bottom-up effort which promoted free and digital access to scientific literature, proposing to go beyond the traditional publishing model controlled by a few publishing companies. The second understanding of openness is related to the institutional response (2010s). In this second phase, the requests of scientists were backed by institutions (such as the EU): Open Science turned into top-down policies. In this context, institutions strongly endorsed the idea of *sharing*, which should not only be limited to journal articles but should extend to many other relevant products of scientific research, such as datasets, models and algorithms. The third understanding of openness is *pluralism*, which is akin to Leonelli’s recent critique of the dominant conceptualization of Open Science as sharing and cumulation of objects (2023, Ch. 4-5). The idea here is to shift the attention from objects to processes informing science. Thus, Open Science should respect and value the epistemic diversity (i.e., the diversity with regard to knowledge production and understanding) of scientific practices. In other words, standards should not be imposed irrespective of the context in which a scientific effort is located. For example, scientists based in low-resourced research environments may reluctantly share their data, with the worry that researchers from more well-funded institutions may use their work without proper recognition. Along with technically improving data sharing, Open Science practices should also ensure that all the contributors are properly credited (Leonelli, 2023, p.21).

In short, we have seen that openness includes many concepts: democratization, sharing, and pluralism. We will not commit to any specific understanding of openness in

Open Science. Yet, we will treasure the idea of openness as pluralism, respect and appreciation of epistemic diversity while performing the FAIRification project of the thesis.

Among Open Science practices, probably one of the most important is FAIR research data management (or data stewardship), that is, the management of research data according to the FAIR principles. FAIR data stewardship is fundamental to ensure the proper sharing and reusability of research data. In the next subsection, we will discuss the concept inspiring FAIR principles, that is, machine-actionability.

2.1.2 Machine-actionability

Good data management is fundamental for scientific discovery and innovation through computational means. Indeed, if we want machines to aid the scientific research process (discovering and analysing data in scale, scope and speed no human could), it is essential that data (and other digital research objects such as metadata or analytical workflows) are *machine-actionable*.

What does machine-actionability mean? When humans discover and process information available online, usually they intuitively recognise contextual cues to understand the meaning of the digital objects (data or something else) they are interacting with. Obviously, machines cannot use intuition but, on the other hand, they are able to accomplish analytical tasks impossible to humans. To fully exploit their computational power, we need to feed machines with information they can handle in the same way as we humans handle a context – in other words, machine-actionable information.

Wilkinson and colleagues use the term “machine-actionable” to refer to “a continuum of possible states wherein a digital object provides increasingly more detailed information to an autonomously acting, computational data explorer” (2016, p.3). In this way, when the computational agent faces a “digital object never encountered before” (*ibid.*), it is able to:

- a) identify the type of object (with respect to both structure and intent), b) determine if it is useful within the context of the agent’s current task by interrogating metadata and/or data elements, c) determine if it is usable, with respect to license, consent, or other accessibility or use constraints, and d) take appropriate action, in much the same manner that a human would. (*ibid.*)

In other words, machine-actionable digital objects ensure that an autonomous computational agent “can make a useful decision” (p.4) regarding never encountered digital objects (data, metadata, infrastructures).

The concept of machine-actionability is the basis of a set of guidelines which emerged in the last decade to specify what good data management means. Namely, the idea is that machines should be able to find, access, interoperate and reuse data with as little human intervention as possible. These guidelines are known as FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). As their creators highlight (Wilkinson et al., 2016, p.4), one virtue of the FAIR principles, unlike previous guidelines for research data management, is their abstractness and domain independence. On the one hand, this virtue led to a broad uptake of the principles. On the other hand, it is not often clear how to implement these principles, as we will discuss later (§2.2).

2.1.3 FAIR Principles

I will now illustrate the FAIR principles, drawing this discussion mostly from the website of GO FAIR, an international bottom-up initiative which curates a detailed specification of the FAIR principles and promotes their implementation across the world (GO FAIR, n.d.), and from Jacobsen et al., 2020a.

There are four FAIR principles, which were first spelt out by Wilkinson and colleagues (2016). Every principle is articulated in several sub-principles. In Table 1, you can find the original statement of the FAIR principles, from Wilkinson et al., 2016, p.4 (Box 2). In these statements, one often finds the term ‘(meta)data’, because, as the GO FAIR website states, these principles apply to data, metadata and infrastructure. The latter may include, as Wilkinson and colleagues (2016) specify, non-data research objects such as algorithms, tools and workflows that produced the data. Generally, in the context of the FAIR principles, the term ‘data’ refers to any digital object or resource and ‘metadata’ refers to “any description of a resource that can serve the purpose of enabling findability and/or reusability and/or interpretation and/or assessment of that resource” (Jacobsen et al., 2020a, p.14).

Now I will discuss each principle and sub-principle. I will follow the order of Table 1, but it will immediately be clear that all the principles and sub-principles are deeply interrelated.

Findability

In order to (re)use data, humans and machines need to discover them easily. To that end, data and metadata have to be automatically findable.

To be Findable:
F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource
To be Accessible:
A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available
To be Interoperable:
I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation
I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data
To be Reusable:
R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

Table 1: The FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016, p.4)

The first step to findability (F1) is assigning a globally unique and persistent identifier “to every element of metadata and every concept/measurement in your dataset” (GO FAIR, n.d.). The identifier thus avoids ambiguity in the meaning of the published (meta)data, both for people, and machines, which will be able to search and integrate published datasets. Concretely, the identifier is an internet link (usually an URL or a URI) which, according to F1, should be, first, globally unique. Namely, the identifier points to your data and your data only, referring to exactly one resource *in the world* and not locally. Second, the identifier should be persistent – unlike many web links which tend to become invalid. Usually, registry services

and dataset repositories guarantee this. Examples of globally unique and persistent identifiers are DOI (DOI Foundation, 2022) and ORCID (ORCID organization, 2025).

Identifiers have different purposes. Sometimes, identifiers refer to scientific *products*, namely documents which constitute the output of scientific research, such as papers or datasets. Identifiers may also refer to scientific *objects* belonging to a certain domain. For example, the life sciences community established UniProt, a knowledge base with unique identifiers for protein sequences (The UniProt Consortium, 2023).¹

The F2 principle invites those who publish the data to describe them with rich metadata, providing information regarding the quality, the context, and the conditions under which the data were generated. Ideally, one should provide metadata such that the data they refer to are findable even without the dataset identifier, in order to enable machines to “discover a resource of interest through, for example, search or filtering” (Jacobsen et al. 2020a, p.15). However, metadata is not only about findability. Below we will see how metadata should be defined for reuse purposes as well (R1).

Since usually data and metadata are in two different files, in the metadata one should also include that dataset’s globally unique and persistent identifier (principle F3). Yet sometimes principles F1-F3 are not enough to guarantee findability on the internet. Therefore, F4 recommends that (meta)data are indexed or registered in a searchable resource, which provides the infrastructure to implement principles F1-F3.

Accessibility

In the FAIR principles, accessibility does not mean that data have to be accessible to anyone (i.e., open). Rather, the idea is that it should be clear under which conditions data can be accessed, even if the access requires authentication or authorization. First of all, (meta)data retrieval should happen through standard and non-proprietary communication protocols, such as HTTPS (A1). If that is not possible for security reasons, it is FAIR to clearly and explicitly provide in the metadata, say, the email of a contact person who can discuss data accessibility.

Subprinciple A1 has several sub-subprinciples which characterize the communication protocol for data access. First, the communication protocol should be open source, no-cost

¹ Such distinction between scientific objects and products is blurry – but it merely has the purpose of giving an idea of the different kinds of things identifiers point to.

and universally implementable (A1.1). Second, the communication protocol should allow for authentication and authorization if needed (A1.2).

One last point regarding accessibility is that metadata should survive the data they refer to (A2). While datasets tend to become invalid over time, because storing and maintaining datasets is costly, metadata are cheaper to maintain. If at least metadata persist, users can track down the people responsible for the upload of the original datasets and possibly regain access to them.

Interoperability

Since scientific research is a cumulative effort, usually the data produced by one laboratory (or researcher) need to be integrated with data produced by someone else. Traditionally, such integration was done manually, by reading papers, writing literature reviews and sometimes compiling datasets derived from several publications. The interoperability principle invites researchers to automatize such processes – in this way, data can interoperate not only with other data but also with “applications or workflows for analysis, storage and processing” (GO FAIR, n.d.). How should this be done?

First, machines should be able to read data and metadata in a standard way. To achieve this, digital objects ought to be represented by a language for knowledge representation with several features (I1). Such language should be formal, namely, its syntax (how to build formulas) and semantics (what the formulas refer to) are explicitly and exactly stipulated by a set of constitutive rules (cf. Iacona, 2021, pp.29-30). Moreover, the specification of such formal language should be shared and accessible by anyone who wants to learn it. Finally, the formal language should work in many scenarios. An example of such language are the specifications of RDF, such as TURTLE or JSON-LD (W3C working group, 2014).

To further ensure interoperability, when describing data or metadata, one should use a vocabulary that should be FAIR too (I2). Here, the term ‘vocabulary’ refers to “any method to unambiguously represent concepts that exist in a given domain” (Jacobsen et al., 2020a, p.21), in a way which is structured and agreed upon by a community. Examples of such methods are flat vocabularies, thesauri, or ontologies. The FAIRness level of the vocabulary used by a specific community should minimally have a globally unique and persistent identifier (F1), accessible through a standardised communication protocol (A1), and described by a language for knowledge representation with the features we just defined (I1).

Finally, to enforce interoperability, (I3) when writing (meta)data it is a good practice to properly cite (using the globally unique identifier) other datasets or metadata in a qualified way, namely making explicit the relationship your (meta)data have with the (meta)data you cite. The purpose of I3 is to create an interlinked network of data and services whose knowledge is connected. We will discuss in more detail interoperability, which will be the focus of our FAIRification project, in §3.2.

Reusability

FAIR principles have the ultimate purpose of data reusability. When making data FAIR, thus, the researchers should ask themselves what their colleagues would need to know to reuse their data (e.g., to replicate their experiments or perform a meta-analysis). Such information is usually provided in the metadata – which, according to R1, should enrich the dataset including a “plurality of accurate and relevant attributes” (GO FAIR, n.d.). Namely, metadata should express the conditions under which the data were generated. R1 builds on F2 but while F2 ensures that the metadata are good enough to find the data, R1 invites the data providers to supply the final user with the information needed to understand if the data are *useful*. Examples of rich metadata include the reason for which it was generated, whether it is raw or processed, with explanations of variable names if needed.

To ensure reusability, the metadata profile should include a clear data usage license, such as Creative Commons (R1.1). This point is about legal interoperability, as opposed to the technical interoperability addressed by the I-related principles. It is important to remember that the absence of a license often entails that a digital object will not be reused for legal reasons. To further specify what rich metadata means, it is always best to include detailed information regarding the provenance (R1.2). Namely, metadata should include who the authors of the dataset are and how they wish to be cited as well as a clear description of the process leading to the data (gathering, processing etc.). The rationale behind providing provenance information is to enable people and machines to assess the usefulness and reusability of a digital object, as well as the condition of proper reuse (Jacobsen et al., 2020a, p. 25).

Usually, scientific data are produced within a community. Thus, R1.3 invites researchers to share their data according to their community standards, which may regard file formats, metadata or vocabulary. Many communities have a set of minimum information standards and if one wants the data to be FAIR, they should at least meet that standard.

In sum, it is clear that the FAIR principles build a solid foundation for machine actionability. If achieved, the FAIR principles “enable machines to make optimal use of data resources” (Jacobsen et al. 2020a, p.13). That is, if a digital object is FAIR, a machine is able to find it through its identifier(s), retrieve it through a standardised communication protocol – and initiate an authentication or authorisation procedure. Moreover, thanks to interoperability, if “two or more digital resources are related to the same topic or entity, it should be possible for machines to merge the information into a richer, unified view of that entity” (Jacobsen et al. 2020a, p.14). Finally, the machine can make a decision regarding the digital object’s usefulness (i.e., is it useful for the task being accomplished?) and usability (i.e., can the digital object be reused and under what conditions?), thanks to the rich metadata specifying provenance, meeting domain-relevant community standards, and including a usage license.

2.1.4 Frameworks for FAIRification

In the last section, we discussed the FAIR principles in detail. As we mentioned above, however, such principles are rather abstract. Some are straightforward to implement (e.g., F3), while others work mostly as a guide (e.g., R1). Due to the abstract nature of the FAIR principles, many efforts (including tools and framework) proliferated (Mangione et al., 2022) to implement FAIRification, i.e., applying FAIR principles. Here we will focus specifically on the frameworks. Some frameworks are thought for specific domains (e.g., Sinaci et al., 2020, for health data), while others are general and domain-agnostic (e.g., Jacobsen et al., 2020b). What further complicates the picture is the fact that it may well be the case that frameworks addressing one domain are applicable to another one, *mutatis mutandis*. Frameworks also differ with regard to the level of abstraction. Some are flexible enough to extend throughout different levels of abstraction (e.g., Welter et al., 2023) while others are more concrete and are immediately applied by their creators to a specific subfield (e.g., He et al., 2023).

Generally, such diversity of application frameworks is expected given the epistemic diversity of science. In other words, the fact that science encompasses many different practices for knowledge production generates a huge diversity in the uptake of the FAIR principles. Providing a whole review of the frameworks would be outside of the scope of this thesis.

Here I will only briefly discuss two important takeaway points from one relevant domain-agnostic framework, designed by Welter and colleagues (2023). The first one is the acknowledgement that a focus on a project improving “every aspect of FAIR is neither useful nor desirable”. Indeed, the idea is that compliance with FAIR principles can only be achieved in the long run. Thus, in the metadata pipeline discussed in Chapter 3 and 4, we will focus mostly on interoperability. The second point is that their FAIRification ‘template’ is useful in order to have an initial idea of a general FAIRification process. Their template consists of 8 steps: get the data; model the domain; select identifier scheme; apply data standards; choose data vocabulary; transform data for interoperability; host data; share data. There is no need to go into the details of each step here, but it suffices to say that their approach instantiates the general idea of FAIR-by-design, according to which one should design the whole data management process in accordance with the FAIR principles from the beginning of a research project.

All in all, combining the ideas of Open Science as pluralism (§2.1.1) and of FAIR-by-design just discussed, we will endorse here a contextual approach, starting from the context of our FAIRification project in materials science, in order to design a FAIR data management process. We will discuss the methodology of contextual FAIRification in §3.1. In the next section, we will discuss the context of our project.

2.2 Context

2.2.1 The Spin-Orbit Torque: Experimental Setup Before FAIRification

In my project at INRiM, I worked on one experiment in the field of spintronics (Fert, 2008), the Spin-Orbit Torque (SOT) measurement (Quiming et al., 2021). Spintronics is a novel kind of electronics which is based not only on the charge of the electron but also on its magnetic spin. This allows to drastically reduce the heat generated by any electrical current, a major problem of traditional electronics. SOT occurs in magnetic thin film devices composed of two layers: a non-magnetic metallic and a magnetic one. When an electric current passes in the non-magnetic layer, due to spin-orbit-coupling (SOC), the electrons get spin-polarized and act as an effective field on the magnetic layer, which alters its magnetisation. In Figure 1a, we see a non-magnetic metallic (NM)/ferromagnetic (FM) bilayer. The electric current J_e generates spin-polarized electrons (S indicates the spin) which act on the magnetization M of the FM layer as two perpendicular magnetic fields ($H_{SOT,FL}$ is the field like torque field, while $H_{SOT,DL}$ is the damping like – for our purposes, the details are

irrelevant). H_{appl} is the externally applied magnetic field. The SOT effect is considered an important game changer for developing a new generation of low energy electronic devices such as magnetic memories and sensors.

The SOT effect can be observed by an electrical resistance change of the non-magnetic layer due to the reciprocal torque effect. Since the effect is dependent on an external magnetic field, for its characterization the resistance measurement is performed in a magnetic field. In particular, for the measurement a so-called Hall bar structure is used (see Fig.1b), which improves the signal-to-noise-ratio due to its structure. The resistance measurement is performed by applying a current J_e and measuring a voltage V_{SOT} . The measurement can be performed at low direct current (0.1-10mA) and in fields up to 100mT. In this way, the material-characteristic SOT efficiency can be determined, a key parameter for spintronic devices.

Figure 1: a) Non-magnetic metallic/ferromagnetic metal bilayer; b) Hall bar

In a SOT measurement, the sample is thus a thin film. The sample is not only composed of two layers: additionally, there are two layers as substrate (that are usually made of silicon and silicon dioxide), below the non-magnetic metallic layer, and one protecting layer (made of, e.g., tantalum) on top of the ferromagnetic layer. An example of a non-magnetic metal is platinum, while an example of ferromagnetic metal is CoFeB.

At INRiM, the laboratory setup of the SOT measurement is controlled by a Python program which activates the instruments to make the current J_e flow and apply the magnetic field (H_{appl}) and the instruments that measure V_{SOT} and thus the resistance. The program automatically writes a .dat file with all the information and draws a plot of the resistance of the NM layer against the magnetization of the FM layer. Right now, all the relevant information regarding the measurement, such as the parameters used for a certain run of the

measurement, the name of the sample and so on, are saved in an unstructured way in a Word file which works as a laboratory notebook. In the next chapter, we will see how we can make this whole setup FAIRer with regard to metadata management.

2.2.2 The Difficulties of FAIRification for Materials Science Data

FAIR tools for data management did not develop equally in all the scientific fields. Even though the FAIR principles are general in scope, many of the authors of the original article (Wilkinson et al., 2016) came from a background in life sciences and bioinformatics. The majority of the examples of FAIR tools they mention relate to life science topics, such as system biology, drug discovery, and the 3D structures of proteins.

Our case study, the SOT measurement, belongs to materials science. Unfortunately, materials science does not have the same quantity of FAIR tools as the life sciences. For example, while the life sciences already have a full-blown repository for ontologies, the OBO Foundry (Jackson et al., 2021), used to systematise ontologies according to common principles, in materials science researchers are just now reviewing existing ontologies (Baas et al., 2023). To cite another example, the FAIR Cookbook (Rocca-Serra et al., 2023), a collection of procedures and methodologies to make scientific data FAIR, which is one of the most valid tools that disseminate knowledge about FAIRification, is targeted to life sciences.

Furthermore, materials science may be divided into two main fields: experimental and computational materials science. Our case study belongs to experimental materials science, which, unlike its computational neighbour, does not have the same number of tools (Ghiringhelli et al., 2023, pp.3-11 for a review of the available tools for computational materials science). In experimental materials science, there are some attempts to extract the results of the past from the published literature (e.g., Gilligan et al., 2023). Yet, despite their value, these works do not contribute to the design of a FAIR-by-design process.

As Ghiringhelli and colleagues (2023) argue, in experimental materials science FAIR metadata should include details on the microstructure and chemical composition of the material, as well as the parameters required to describe the state of the instruments. However, the majority of the instruments used in laboratories worldwide provide data and metadata in a proprietary format, which is difficult to convert to other formats without loss of information. Where the instruments are custom built, scientists are agreeing on the use of certain formats, for example, NeXus (Könnecke et al., 2015), which was initially used for

neutron, x-ray, and muon data, but it is spreading to other fields. NeXus data format enables the organization of data in HDF5 according to some domain-specific rules. Another interesting tool is the repository and archive NOMAD, which was born as a tool for computations on innovative materials, but it is slowly expanding to experiments. As we will see in Chapter 3, NOMAD is a component of the metadata pipeline.

All in all, despite the slow uptake of useful tools from neighbouring fields, we witness a scarcity of the availability of resources for FAIRification in the field of experimental materials science, which in general has a low digital maturity as opposed to closer (computational materials science) and further (life sciences) scientific areas. This scarcity of resources, as well as the fact that in an emerging field of study it is difficult to understand the direction of a fruitful research project, is the main constraint within which the project described in this thesis took place.

2.3 FAIR Infrastructure as an Enabling Condition for Data Science

It should now be clear that the FAIRification work done in this thesis is different from a traditional data science project. The FAIRification process bears some similarities with traditional extraction, transform, and load (ETL) processes and data integration within the field of data analysis for business intelligence. However, the main difference is that in that case, data scientists work within a *closed* system. Usually, they know the different data sources that will be used to build the data warehouse, and they know the business objectives that guide the design of a business intelligence analytics chain. On the contrary, a data steward who is undertaking a FAIRification project is working in the *open* system of scientific research: the data steward does not know what the other possible sources of data are and how the data will be reused. Traditional data analysis is about building architecture, while data stewardship is about building infrastructure.

Indeed, rather than analysis itself, FAIR principles inform the design and development of an infrastructure to *enable* fruitful data science. The fact that data, metadata, and in general any digital object associated with scientific research are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable makes them ready to be analysed and studied. The general idea is that FAIRness in scientific data will uncover their untapped potential, enhancing the reusability of data and new scientific discoveries.

In this chapter, I illustrated the background concepts (Open Science, FAIR principles, FAIRification) and context (SOT measurement, experimental materials science)

useful to understand the result of this project, which is the metadata pipeline that will be illustrated in the next chapter.

Chapter 3

Method and Tools

In the last chapter, I discussed the necessary background to understand the work done and the main difficulties encountered in the FAIRification of materials science data. In this chapter, I will illustrate the methodology and the tools we adopted to build – within the contextual boundaries – the metadata pipeline, which transfers metadata from the computational environment of the data production to the one of data sharing and will be presented in Chapter 4.

The methodology conceived for this project is a particular understanding of FAIRification, namely contextual FAIRification, which takes into account existing frameworks but adapts the FAIRification process to the scientific context at hand (§3.1). Contextual FAIRification, along with other frameworks, implies the choice of a particular focus. In our case, the focus is metadata and interoperability, which I will explain in §3.2, including related relevant concepts. Successively (§3.3), I will describe each of the tools used to build the metadata pipeline: the conceptual metadata standard (§3.3.1), CHADA, a metadata standard developed by a group of academic and industrial stakeholders for materials characterization measurements and experiments (Comité Européen de Normalisation, 2021); an electronic laboratory notebook (ELN), eLabFTW (CARPi et al., 2017), used to initially gather metadata (§3.3.2); and NOMAD (Scheidgen et al., 2023), an archive for materials science data (§3.3.3).

3.1 Contextual FAIRification

In the last chapter, we explained the fragmented context of FAIR tools in experimental materials science, as opposed to other scientific fields. Moreover, we highlighted how the most recent conceptualisation of Open Science (Leonelli, 2023; Paseri, 2024) understands openness as pluralism and respect of epistemic diversity in scientific practices. Furthermore, recall that from the last chapter (§2.1.4), our aim is to build a FAIR-by-design FAIRification process. On this basis, we hold that the methodology most appropriate for our FAIRification project is *contextual* FAIRification, namely the design of FAIR research process from the context – rather than the application of an abstract workflow (such as the one of Welter et al., 2023). This is the reason why we described the context of our project in Chapter 2.2.

Despite the variety of FAIRification frameworks (cf. §2.1.4), our contextual approach should still use the other frameworks as guides. In a recent poster, which contains the first comparison among FAIRification frameworks, Vieira and colleagues (2023) identified three critical common steps for a FAIRification project: identifying objectives; the definition and assessment of (meta)data standards and semantic modelling; definition of a data license. We will roughly use these three steps as a guide within contextual FAIRification.

Indeed, in our methodology, after the study of the context, we decided a goal for our project. As mentioned, the idea of defining the goal of FAIRification is common among many frameworks (Jacobsen et al., 2020b; Welter et al., 2023). Welter and colleagues (2023) suggest that a good FAIRification goal should be realistic and practical and thus have a clear aim, scope, and expected scientific value. In our FAIRification project, the aim and the expected scientific value coincide, i.e., the exploration of the FAIRification in a field with a rather low digital maturity (spintronics, within experimental materials science). Furthermore, the scope of the exploration was metadata and interoperability – even though, as we will see in Chapter 4, taking care of interoperability has consequences also for the other aspects of FAIR. In sum, the goal was defined by only focusing on two specific aspects of FAIR research data management, namely metadata and interoperability.

For the other critical steps of FAIRification (namely, definition and assessment of metadata standards, semantic modelling and licensing) we used several tools which will be described in §3.3. Before delving into that, in the next section we will explore in more detail the concepts of metadata and interoperability, which will help clarify the focus of our FAIRification project.

3.2 Focus: Metadata and Interoperability

In this section I will discuss the focus of our project, namely metadata and interoperability, by illustrating these concepts, along with the concept of ontology. Eventually, this discussion will lead us to the kind of interoperability, i.e., modest interoperability, we aimed to achieve in our FAIRification project.

Let us start with the concept of metadata. Metadata are usually defined as data about the data, that is, information that describes a certain data object or dataset. To be more precise, metadata are statements or descriptions about an object which is potentially informative (Pomerantz, 2015, p.26). To make an everyday example, think about the pictures you take with your smartphone camera. When the smartphone saves the picture, usually you

can tap on the ‘information’ button and see the time and the location of the picture, as well as the size of the file. Beyond this mundane example, metadata have a crucial role in science.

Scientific publication often entails sharing datasets, which usually need the respective paper to be properly understood. For example, you may read in the column heading “Temperature” – but you often need to go back to the paper to see whether the units are Celsius, Fahrenheit, or Kelvin or whether the measurement refers, say, to the environmental conditions or the sample. The FAIR principles strongly recommend a careful and structured use of metadata to encapsulate this kind of information – so that one can properly interpret a dataset and decide about its usefulness without checking the paper it relates to.

Ideally, according to the FAIR principles, metadata should not only allow human interpretation and action, but they should also be machine-actionable (cf. §2.1.2): namely, a machine should be able to read and make decisions about unfamiliar data objects thanks to the metadata associated with such objects. Metadata are thus of paramount importance for the implementation of the FAIR principles and have been described as the “cornerstones of the FAIR principles” (Batista et al. 2022, p.1).

To give a more precise idea of what metadata are, we can look at the definition of Ghiringhelli and colleagues (2023): “Metadata are attributes that are necessary to locate, fully characterize, and ultimately reproduce other attributes that are identified as data” (p.2). First, metadata should provide provenance information, which describes the steps needed to determine the data. Second, metadata should characterize their data objects such that it is clear whether two objects are comparable with regard to a given attribute value. Third, metadata should be used to reproduce the experiment they refer to.

This definition resonates with the classic taxonomy of metadata. Usually, metadata are divided into *descriptive metadata*, providing a general description of the object they refer to (e.g., the kind of resource: dataset, book, etc.), *structural metadata*, describing the structure of the data (e.g., the headers of a table), and *administrative metadata*, providing information on the provenance of the data, e.g., the history, versioning, etc. (Pomerantz, 2015, pp.17-18).

In practice, metadata constitute a schema, usually a dictionary composed of key-value pairs.² FAIR principles suggest several implications for such schema, which were already discussed in the last chapter. Here I will focus on interoperability. As summarized by Ghiringhelli and colleagues (2023), interoperability “implies the use of formal, accessible,

² It would be best if such metadata schema were machine-actionable, as advocated by Batista et al. (2022).

shared, and broadly applicable languages for knowledge representation [I1] (...), use of vocabularies to annotate data and metadata [I2], and inclusion of references [I3]" (*ibidem*). Interoperability is ultimately about the possibility of integrating independently conceived pieces of information in order to analyse them (Guizzardi, 2020, p.183). In particular, semantic interoperability ensures that two information systems are, so to say, 'speaking the same language'. For example, let us imagine that a machine is comparing two datasets. In each dataset, there is a column labelled "Temperature". But in dataset A, "Temperature" refers to the sample temperature, while in dataset B it refers to the environmental conditions. If a machine parses these data without further information, it may well understand these columns to refer to the same thing and treat them equally in its meta-analysis of the two datasets, eventually generating misleading results.

More precisely, according to Guizzardi (2020) – whose ideas are successively developed by Guizzardi and Guarino (2024) – semantic interoperability is connected to the idea of ontological commitment, a philosophical concept first coined by Quine (1948), and successively adopted in computer science by Mealy (1967). The idea here is that a certain theory or description of the world has an ontological commitment to certain entities, namely those entities that the theory must be able to refer to if the propositions of the theory are true. Thus, a presupposition for semantic interoperability is the possibility to specify the ontological commitments embedded in different information systems A and B. According to Guizzardi,

two systems A and B semantically interoperate if the coded relations connecting the information structures of A and B: (i) preserve the semantics of the referents represented in those structures; (ii) reflect the real-world meta-properties of the represented relations; and (iii) yield a resulting information structure that constraints the possible states of the resulting system to the intended ones, i.e., to those that represent intended state of affairs according to the conceptualizations underlying A and B." (Guizzardi, 2020, p.185)

This aim is ambitious and well worthy of pursuit. Indeed, we may agree that, as advocated by Guizzardi (2020, p. 189), to achieve full interoperability one should find a way to make explicit the ontological commitments of informational systems and make ontologically consistent connections. However, following the interpretation of FAIR principles as an ideal that can be achieved only in the long run (as explained in §2.1.4), here we would like to adhere to a more modest understanding and implementation of interoperability.

To address the issue of (semantic) interoperability, FAIR principles endorse the use of controlled vocabularies (I2) referencing other relevant sources (I3), via the use of a formal, accessible, shared and broadly applicable language (I1). The term ‘vocabulary’ may refer to a flat list of definitions but also to more structured ways to organize information, such as ontologies (Jacobsen et al. 2020a, p.22). In the computer science community, ontologies are structural organizations of terms in a given domain, which are deemed to represent real-world entities through classes and properties (Russel and Norvig, 2020).³

Using a controlled vocabulary or an ontology satisfies some of the desiderata that drive the “T” of FAIR, namely clarity (I1) and unambiguity (I2) with regard to the terms (which may refer to entities, steps in the research process, and so on) that are used in the data and metadata. As we will see shortly, this often amounts to the choice of a certain standard in the gathering of metadata. Moreover, ideally such metadata should be able to meaningfully interact with other metadata from other experiments, for example via qualified reference (I3). For example, if in my experiment I am studying the properties of a sample containing silicon dioxide, ideally, I would like to query other experiments with such substance. Yet, this does not mean that such query may satisfy semantic interoperability in the strong sense advocated by Guizzardi. Still, a weaker implementation of semantic interoperability may help machines to discriminate meanings in predicaments like the issue of temperature as the “temperature of the sample” vs “temperature of the environment”. Here we will not attempt any rigorous characterization of modest interoperability, but we will consider something as modestly interoperable if it strives to satisfy the desiderata of clarity, unambiguity, and qualified reference, what may be loosely called the spirit of the “T” principle.

In summary, the focus of our FAIRification project was metadata and interoperability because our project aimed to design a *metadata* pipeline that strives to adhere as much as possible to the spirit of the *interoperability* principle (i.e., modest interoperability), within the technical and contextual constraints described in §2.2. I will describe the metadata pipeline in Chapter 4. Before that, in the following sections I will explain the tools we used to build it.

³ Arguably, ontologies – in the computer science sense – do not necessarily make explicit the ontological commitments of an information system – but discussing this would go beyond the scope of this thesis.

3.3 Tools

In §3.1, among the critical steps of FAIRification, we mentioned definition and assessment of metadata standards, semantic modelling and licensing. As far as licensing is concerned, we will upload our metadata in a repository for materials science (NOMAD) which publishes the material with the CC-BY-4.0 license (Creative Commons organization, n.d.).

In our case, the metadata standard (or, as we will call it, metadata schema) is CHADA, a document we will describe and assess shortly (§3.3.1). Semantic modelling deserves a few extra words. Usually, semantic modelling refers to a process according to which one “specifies the broader context of a data source” (Hoseini et al., 2024, p. 4). The basic idea is that one has to create relationships (or matching) – usually understood as a set of subject-predicate-object triples – between the structural element of a data source (e.g., the column of a table) and a vocabulary, a thesaurus or an ontology. Usually, semantic modelling also involves specifying further meaningful relationships (also as subject-predicate-object triples) between the concepts of the data source (e.g., between two different columns of the same table) that go beyond the ones present in the reference vocabulary/thesaurus/ontology. Jacobsen and colleagues (2020b, p.60) unpack the process of semantic modelling in three steps: creation of a (non-machine-actionable) conceptual model; search of appropriate ontology terms; creation of the semantic model (machine-actionable). Semantic modelling is one of the traditional ways to reach interoperability.

In our case, we followed a different approach – only partially connected to semantic modelling. The reason for this is contextual. Indeed, in materials sciences there are not ontology search engines, such as the Ontology Lookup Service for biomedical ontologies (European Bioinformatics Institute, n.d.). As Ghiringhelli and colleagues (2023) report, there are only several domain-specific ontologies (unrelated to spintronics) and one of the promising domain-agnostic ontology for materials science, EMMO (Elemental Multiperspective Material Ontology) was not connected to existing databases. Rather than traditional semantic modelling through ontologies, at the moment the best option to reach interoperability in the fields of materials science is probably the adoption of NOMAD. NOMAD is a widely used archive, and it enables the sharing of data and metadata in an interoperable way, by semantically enriching data and metadata with the NOMAD Metainfo, as we will see in §3.3.3.

Before describing NOMAD, in the next sections we will describe the tools used for our FAIRification project.

3.3.1 The conceptual metadata schema: CHADA

As we will see in the next chapter, to build the first step of the pipeline we have to adopt a common conceptual standard for writing metadata. Since our experimental case study is a measurement, we could adopt the VIM, the international vocabulary of metrology (JCGM, 2012). However, the VIM contains only highly general terms and concepts of metrology (such as, ‘quantity’ and ‘measurement unity’) and thus it is not sufficient for the SOT measurement. We need to adopt a more specific conceptual standard.

Since the SOT measurement is a measurement in material characterization, namely the field of materials science that focuses on identifying and measuring the properties of materials, we decided to adopt the standard known as CHADA, an acronym for Characterisation Data. Such standard for materials characterization experiments and measurements was established by a group of academic and industrial stakeholders in the CEN (European Committee for Standardization) Workshop Agreement (CWA) 17815:2021 (Comité Européen de Normalisation, 2021).⁴ The CHADA was presented in an earlier article by Romanos and colleagues (2019). We called it ‘conceptual’ in that it is a PDF document (thus it is human-intelligible but not machine-actionable) and it provides guidelines for organizing the metadata from domain experts, in a narrative and abstract way, without reference to the computational format with which the metadata should be gathered.

The CEN CWA 17815:2021 contains two main parts. The first is a vocabulary and the second consists in the actual documentation for materials characterisation methods (CHADA). The vocabulary contains the definitions of common terms used in the CHADA. For example, “Probe” is defined as “the physical tool (i.e., a disturbance, primary solicitation, or a gadget), controlled over time, that generate measurable fields that interact with the sample to acquire information on sample’s behaviour and properties.” (Comité Européen de Normalisation, 2021, p.12). Often, the definitions reference other relevant definitions from other global standards (such as the ISO ones). For example, the definition of material characterization is “Broad and general process of collecting existing information about a material’s chemistry, structure, and other properties, and if appropriate, new data, to facilitate the evaluation of these properties” (Comité Européen de Normalisation, 2021, p.9), which

⁴ In January 2025, there was an update with regard to the CHADA (Comité Européen de Normalisation, 2025) but the majority of the work was done before such update, so we will stick to the 2021 version. This notwithstanding, the basic structure of the metadata pipeline is independent of the specifics of the conceptual metadata standard.

cites the standard EN ISO 10993-1. Since the definitions of the terms refer to other relevant definitions, the CHADA satisfies the I3 of the FAIR principles.

After the definitions of the relevant terms, the document provides the CHADA, which organizes the metadata into four sections: ‘user case’, ‘experiment’, ‘raw data’, and ‘data processing’. Every section contains other fields to be filled in documenting the material characterization process. These four families of concepts are intended to be the building blocks of the description of any possible characterization method: they can be combined freely and iteratively. The ‘user case’ provides an essential description of the sample (in particular, the material properties such as chemical composition and microstructure), the environment, and the users performing the measurement. The ‘experiment’ section describes mostly the physical process that enables the measurement, namely the interaction between the probe, the sample, the signal, and the detector. The ‘raw data’ describes the data table produced through the experiment, with the column headers (the variables measured) and the units. The last section, ‘data processing’ describes any manipulation of the raw data table, e.g., analysis, and processing through calibration.

The CHADA is a good metadata schema in that it prescribes to provide provenance information, the characterization of the data objects and – since it is the result of a collective effort – information useful to reproduce the experiment. In particular, it is also a good standard for experimental materials science because it has elements regarding the material, its history, and parameters for measurement, information deemed desirable by Ghiringhelli and colleagues (2023, p.12). One possible limit of CHADA is its generality. It would be best if in the future a specific metadata schema for spintronics would be designed.

3.3.2 The Electronic Laboratory Notebook: eLabFTW

Another fundamental tool for the pipeline (which we will use to make CHADA machine-actionable, cf. §4.2.2) is the electronic laboratory notebook eLabFTW (CARPi et al., 2017). ELNs are useful tools towards FAIRification, in that they provide an infrastructure to produce machine-actionable records of experimental activities (Higgins et al., 2022), enabling FAIR-by-design research.

In particular, eLabFTW has some interesting relevant features.⁵ The main object types of eLabFTW are experiments and resources. Experiments are the records of an experimental activity, while resources are objects with the purpose of organizing things, such

⁵ Much of the information on the functioning of eLabFTW comes from the documentation (CARPi, 2012).

as chemicals or instruments, which are used in a given experiment. While experiments can be created by any user, resources can only be created by admins.

Minimally, an experiment is composed of the title and the main text content (which may be empty), which is a description of the experiment, achieved through a rich-text editor. To each experiment, eLabFTW assigns a unique immutable ID (locally). Thus, the experiments are locally findable. Experiments may be assigned categories and tags (e.g., to organize different projects) and status (e.g., running, need to be redone, success, fail). Experiments can refer to resources or other experiments. Moreover, one can list all the steps needed for the workflow. All these features are potentially interesting for actual work performed on eLabFTW. Yet, since the aim of our project was mostly exploratory on the FAIRification potential of eLabFTW, we focused on how this ELN enables metadata recording.

Indeed, as far as metadata are concerned, the most interesting feature of eLabFTW is the possibility to attach custom JSON metadata to the experiment. These metadata are called ‘extra_fields’. One can add as many ‘key: value’ pairs as desired. There are of course several kinds of datatypes allowed (number, text, select, etc.). And one can group the ‘extra_fields’ in different partitions.

Moreover, another important feature of eLabFTW we deployed was the possibility of creating an experiment template for the kinds of experiments often performed. For example, the experiment template may contain empty metadata keys (inserted via the ‘extra_fields’) to be filled with a specific value every time the experiment is performed. From the experiment template, then, one can create a specific instance of the experiment. All in all, the customization of the metadata and the creation of experiment templates are the most relevant features of eLabFTW for our FAIRification purposes. In Figure 2, we can see a portion of a customised experiment template in eLabFTW. Additionally, it was really important for our purpose the fact that eLabFTW allowed the use of API. The API integration we implemented will be described in §4.2.2.

Figure 2: Portion of customised experiment template in eLabFTW (SOT measurement).

3.3.3 NOMAD

As we will see in §4.2.2, eLabFTW will be used to host the metadata of the SOT measurement locally. The next step is to understand how to make the data and metadata available to others, which is a crucial aspect of Open Science. Indeed, FAIR principles may arguably be seen as a way to enhance data sharing among scientific communities. To facilitate open data sharing, many repositories were developed. One prominent example is Zenodo (European Organization For Nuclear Research & OpenAIRE, 2013), a general-purpose repository maintained by the CERN, first designed for research funded by the European Commission but successively adopted by many researchers and institutions around the world. Zenodo was created as part of an Open Science initiative, and it is committed to the FAIR principles. One of the main advantages of Zenodo is the fact that for every published item (a paper, a presentation, a dataset), the repository assigns a DOI. However, as even the main developer suggests (Nielsen, 2017), it would be better to consider domain-specific repositories before uploading research results on Zenodo. Furthermore, Zenodo only requests minimal and generic metadata to publish a record (e.g., ‘Resource type’, ‘Title’, and ‘Publication date’). Hence, Zenodo does not adopt metadata standards that enable the kind of interoperability advocated by the FAIR principles. Thus, to publish the metadata from our pipeline, we opted for NOMAD, an open-source, domain-specific and interoperable repository for materials science (Scheidgen et al., 2023).

NOMAD has been online since 2014 and it was initially designed for simulations in materials science but is now being developed to include experimental materials science, the field to which the SOT measurement belongs. Like Zenodo, the purpose of NOMAD is to make scientific research data FAIR. One of the main advantages of NOMAD (as opposed

to Zenodo) is that it directly extracts the data from different file formats. The extracted data becomes then machine-actionable. In this way, also the metadata becomes part of the data itself. NOMAD has the advantage of recognizing the porosity of the data/metadata distinction and the fact that today's metadata may become tomorrow's data. Thus, the metadata we gathered in our metadata pipeline will be uploaded as data to NOMAD.

How does NOMAD work, in practice? As the documentation explains (NOMAD Lab, n.d.-a), initially the user creates an upload, which is analogous to a project. The user can upload many raw files in a single upload. If a raw file has a format recognized by NOMAD, then it is called a mainfile, and NOMAD creates a database (or archive) entry for that file. In the creation of an entry, the mainfile is processed. The processing mainly consists of parsing and normalizing. A parser recognises the data in the mainfile and transforms it into a tree of data called archive entry or processed data (see Fig. 3 for an example of archive entry). Sometimes this process is automatic, but it is often the case that one has to program one's own parser, for example with tabular data. A normalizer is a program that runs on processed data, manipulates it and expands it on the basis of the information already present in the general NOMAD archive.

The screenshot displays three panels in the NOMAD interface. The left panel shows a navigation menu for an 'Entry' section, with 'data' selected. The middle panel, titled 'SOTMeasurement', shows a 'data' sub-section with the following fields: 'short name' (SOT_attempt_API), 'composite system reference' (thin_film.archive.json), 'UserCase Sample sample name' (09/D6), 'datetime' (28/02/2025 18:34), and 'Experiment RunNumber' (11). The right panel, titled 'Sample Structure', shows a 'SampleStructure' section with 'QUANTITIES' including 'name = thin_film', 'UserCase Sample device width = 100000 Å', 'UserCase Sample device length = 1.03·10⁻⁶ Å', 'ID', and 'UserCase Sample device geometry = Hall bar'. Both the middle and right panels have a 'REFERENCED BY' button labeled 'closed'.

Figure 3: Example of archive entry in NOMAD

The main advantage of NOMAD is that it enables an advanced level of interoperability. Just with a rapid glimpse at the filter on the explore page, we can see how we can filter many entries published by many people on a specific material through the presence or the absence of a certain chemical element or substance (see Fig. 4). Such level of interoperability is extremely important to enable data-intensive scientific discovery, for example with regard to new materials – as advocated by Scheffler et al., 2022. The features of NOMAD align with modest interoperability and the spirit of the ‘I’ of FAIR – striving to satisfy the desiderata of clarity, unambiguity and qualified reference. Another advantage of NOMAD is that it can also be used as an ELN. However, unlike eLabFTW, it is not user-

friendly and rather complex, and it requires programming. For this reason, the best thing a data steward can do to facilitate the work of scientists is to design metadata pipelines that move data and metadata between eLabFTW and NOMAD at least semi-automatically.

Figure 4: Example of filter in the search page of NOMAD

To fully exploit the interoperability potential of NOMAD, we used the NOMAD Metainfo, which is the NOMAD schema language used to structure its data and that we will now briefly describe.⁶ NOMAD data is structured into sections. Every section follows a given definition that constrains the kind of data that can be accommodated in that section. In other words, a section definition defines a class of data. Every entry has two kinds of properties: quantities (i.e., slots for specific datatypes) and subsections. To enhance interoperability, sections often inherit the properties of other sections. The entry shown in Figure 3 has three sections: ‘Entry’, ‘SOTMeasurement’, and ‘Sample Structure’. The section ‘Entry’ contains three subsections: ‘results’, ‘metadata’, ‘data’. The ‘data’ section contains the section ‘SOTMeasurement’, which has five quantities: ‘short name’, ‘composite system reference’, ‘UserCase Sample sample name’, ‘datetime’, ‘Experiment RunNumber’. The ‘composite system reference’ creates a reference to another section, ‘Sample Structure’, with four quantities: ‘name’, ‘UserCase Sample device width’, ‘UserCase Sample device length, and ‘UserCase Sample device geometry’.

Figure 3 shows an entry with sections that rely on section *definitions*. There are three categories of definitions in NOMAD. First, there are sections defining the shared entry

⁶ To illustrate the data structure of NOMAD we will follow the documentation (NOMAD Lab, n.d.-b).

structure, which are agnostic with regard to the specific data. One example of that is the ‘EntryData’ section, which is used to add new top-level sections to an entry. Second, we have base sections, which refer to shared common concepts and are namely sections that are reusable in other section definitions. For example, the ‘ElnBaseSection’ is a section that provides common properties to ELN entries, e.g., the quantities ‘name’ and ‘datetime’. The creators of NOMAD encourage the reuse of section definitions which define common concepts. One can browse the base sections in the Metainfo (NOMAD Lab, n.d.-c) and can see that the base sections are organized in a structured way. The idea is that the more the researchers publish data from different kinds of experiments or simulations, using different methods, the more the Metainfo will be rich, and the section definitions will be reused. Third, there are the specific schemas designed for a certain purpose. Specific schema packages enable the customization of a NOMAD entry as desired by the user. A package is a collection of section definitions. In other words, schema packages are like a blueprint of the way one wants to insert the data into NOMAD. Again, the specific schema should reuse the base sections as much as possible. The NOMAD user, then, should define a schema package and upload it in an entry to enable structured data inputs. This is exactly what we did to build our pipeline. In Chapter 4 (§4.2.3), we will describe a relevant part of the schema package we used for the metadata pipeline.

All in all, the reuse of section definitions through the NOMAD Metainfo enables the same kind of interoperability we would have by using traditional semantic modelling. In the NOMAD case, instead of having a reference ontology, we have the NOMAD Metainfo with all the relevant reusable and structurally connected section definitions. Moreover, NOMAD provides an environment to share one’s own data and metadata with a DOI, and access data from other sources.

In summary, in this chapter, we have explained the methods and tools used to build our FAIRification project, i.e., the metadata pipeline. First, we described the general methodology, contextual FAIRification, namely the idea of building a FAIR-by-design process by starting from the context rather than instantiating a general profile. Then we discussed the focus of our project on metadata and interoperability. Finally, we described each of the tools used to build the metadata pipeline: CHADA, eLabFTW, and NOMAD. In the next chapter, we will see how the tools fit together to build the metadata pipeline for the SOT measurement.

Chapter 4

Result: The Metadata Pipeline

In the last chapter, I discussed the methodology and the tools necessary to build the metadata pipeline within the contextual limits of FAIRification in experimental materials science. In this chapter, I will show how CHADA, eLabFTW and NOMAD assemble in the metadata pipeline, shown in Figure 5. As already mentioned, the envisioned pipeline transfers metadata from the computational environment of the data production (the laboratory Python program) to the one of data sharing (NOMAD). This pipeline will be semi-automatic, and it may be considered a cornerstone for future applications.

I will start with an overview of the metadata pipeline for the SOT measurement (§4.1). Successively, I will proceed by describing each element of the pipeline (§4.2). Roughly, the metadata pipeline consists of three steps. The first step is the definition of a flat conceptual metadata schema by adopting the CHADA to the SOT measurement (§4.2.1). The second step amounts to the creation of a template in eLabFTW on the basis of the flat conceptual metadata schema, as well as the creation of the experiment from the template with the metadata from the laboratory Python program. The third step is the sharing of the eLabFTW experiment in NOMAD, which enables data sharing in a partially interoperable way (4.2.3).

4.1 An Overview of the Metadata Pipeline for the Spin-Orbit Torque Measurement

In this section, I will provide a general description of the metadata pipeline, shown in Figure 5, in which every component of the metadata pipeline is either an action to be taken (i.e., a step, represented by a rectangle) or an input of the process (represented by an ellipse and referenced with letters). As we mentioned in Chapter 2 (§2.2.1), the experimental setup of the measurement is controlled by a Python program, which controls the instruments generating the input to the measurement (i.e., direct currents) and reading the output (i.e., voltages). The Python laboratory program produces a .dat file containing the data. As we mentioned in §3.2, we decided to focus our pipeline only on the *metadata*. However, with few

extra steps that we will discuss at the end of this section this pipeline can be extended also to the data itself.

All the relevant information – for every run of the measurement, every sample measured, every data table produced, and every plot made – is now registered in natural language in a Word file. How can one make the metadata of this measurement FAIRer – especially with regard to interoperability?

First, we have to adopt a common conceptual standard for writing metadata (cf. Fig. 5, Step 1). Since the spin-orbit torque (SOT) is a measurement in material characterization, namely the field of materials science that focuses on identifying and measuring the properties of materials, we decided to adopt CHADA (cf. Fig. 5, A), the standard we discussed in §3.3.1. However, the CHADA is written in natural language, and it is not machine-actionable. We adapted the CHADA to the case of the SOT measurement, bearing in mind the experimental needs (cf. Fig. 5, B), i.e. those metadata that are relevant to the measurement but that the CHADA may not mention. In this way, we defined a flat conceptual metadata schema, a list of keys for a potential metadata dictionary.

Figure 5: Metadata pipeline.

The FAIRification process was enhanced thanks to the use, in the Step 2 of the pipeline, of an Electronic Laboratory Notebook (ELN), which is meant to substitute the paper laboratory notebook or, in our case, the Word file natural language notebook. The chosen ELN was the open-source software eLabFTW (CARPi et al., 2017), with which one can build experiment templates, with the possibility to add customized metadata fields (cf. §3.3.2). Deploying this feature of eLabFTW, the flat conceptual metadata schema was then used to build the eLabFTW template for the SOT measurement (cf. Fig. 5, Step 2a).

Successively, a Python script was developed to implement an API integration between the laboratory Python program (cf. Fig. 5, C) and eLabFTW. Through an API POST command in the Python script, an experiment from the template previously designed was created (cf. Fig. 5, Step 2b). Then, some of the values of the empty metadata fields in the template were filled with information from the laboratory Python program (cf. Fig. 5, C), while some of them were inserted by the user's metadata entry (cf. Fig. 5, D). We end up with an eLabFTW experiment with all the desired metadata.

Then we faced the issue of how to publish the metadata in a FAIR way – in particular, in an interoperable way. Since Zenodo lacks adequate metadata standards, as explained in §3.3.3, we chose NOMAD (Scheidgen et al., 2023) as the platform to publish our metadata (step 3 of the pipeline). As mentioned in §3.3.3, through NOMAD one can not only publish data and metadata with a DOI, but also make them interoperable thanks to the NOMAD Metainfo, its schema language. However, to properly create a NOMAD schema for the experiment, we had to match, when possible, the key of the eLabFTW template with the NOMAD Metainfo (cf. Fig. 5, Step 3a). Then, on the basis of this matching, we created a custom NOMAD schema to actually make our metadata interoperable (cf. Fig. 5, Step 3b). Finally, thanks to API integration, the information present in eLabFTW was retrieved and uploaded into NOMAD (cf. Fig. 5, Step 3c). The details will be explained below.

As we mentioned above, this pipeline only pertains to metadata. It is possible, however, to extend this pipeline to data. Indeed, the eLabFTW API allows the upload of the .dat file, and it would be possible to write a parser in NOMAD for tabular data, creating a visualization. We will now turn to analyse more in detail the metadata pipeline.

4.2 Design of the Pipeline

4.2.1 Step 1: Flat conceptual metadata schema

In adapting the CHADA (described in §3.3.1) to the SOT measurement (cf. Fig. 5, A), we established a flat conceptual metadata schema (cf. Fig. 5, Step 1). Roughly, such schema is a list of keys or fields that will then be filled with the values coming from the experimental process. The metadata schema is conceptual in that for now we are still not concerned with machine-actionability. We thought through what every field of the CHADA may mean for our measurement. Moreover, we added some relevant parameters that have no direct links to the CHADA, such as the magnetic field direction with regard to the current flowing through the sample. Indeed, we believe it is important to bear in mind the experimental needs deriving from the context of the measurement we are documenting, because it may well be the case that important parameters for the context at hand are not explicitly discussed in the chosen metadata standard (cf. Fig. 5, B).

Furthermore, despite the fact that the CHADA subdivides the metadata keys or fields in groups (e.g., ‘Sample’ is included in ‘User case’) we decided not to impose it. Thus, our conceptual metadata schema is *flat*. The reason behind this choice is that the following steps of the metadata pipeline do not allow groups in a way that is meaningful for interoperability. As we will see below, the chosen ELN only allows one level of grouping for the metadata fields. However, we retained the information regarding the section and subsections of the CHADA in the way we named the keys, using a combination of underscore and CamelCase notation. An object for future research may be to find a way to bring the groups envisioned in the CHADA all the way down in the metadata pipeline. For illustrative purposes, Figure 6 contains a portion of the keys of the flat conceptual metadata standard.

```
Experiment_RunNumber
Experiment_DateAndTime
UserCase_SamplePreparation
Experiment_InteractionVolume
Experiment_CalibrationProcess
UserCase_CharacterisationEnvironment
Experiment_Probe&PhysicsOfInteraction_probe_1
Experiment_Probe&PhysicsOfInteraction_probe_2
Experiment_Detector_detector_1
Experiment_Detector_detector_2
```

Figure 6: Portion of the flat conceptual metadata schema

4.2.2 Step 2: The use of eLabFTW in the SOT measurement metadata pipeline

We have now defined a flat list of keys that have to be filled with the values derived from the experimental process. To achieve this, we use a machine-actionable tool, namely the electronic laboratory notebook eLabFTW (CARPi et al., 2017), which we described in §3.3.2.

We inserted every key of the flat conceptual metadata schema in the ‘extra_fields’ of a new experiment template (cf. Fig. 5, Step 2a). Now, we would like for at least some values of the keys to be completed automatically when a SOT measurement is performed.

To achieve this, we developed an API integration between eLabFTW and the Python program controlling the laboratory setup (cf. Fig. 5, C).⁷ We used the Python library developed ad hoc for the eLabFTW REST API (CARPi, 2022). In the script, we first GET the experiment template, then POST an experiment from the experiment template (cf. Fig. 5, Step 2b). Successively, we edit the empty metadata from the experiment template with the values of variables coming from the Python lab program. To ensure metadata quality, we transform some of the lab program values into human-readable values for our metadata (e.g., the string ‘LONG’, referring to the magnetic field direction, becomes ‘Longitudinal with regard to the current’). Finally, we PATCH the experiment created with the edited metadata. This API integration – if added to the lab Python program – enables the automatic creation of an experimental record in the ELN whenever the measurement is run. In particular, the API integration fills automatically the values of the following fields in the eLabFTW experiment:

- ‘Experiment_DateAndTime’,
- ‘Experiment_RunNumber’,
- ‘Experiment_MeasurementParameters_field_direction’,
- ‘UserCase_Sample_sample_name’,
- ‘Experiment_MeasurementParameters_current_pulse’,
- Experiment_MeasurementParameters_magnetic_field_sequence.

Obviously, not all the metadata come from the lab Python program. The rest of the metadata (such as ‘Experiment_Probe&PhysicsOfInteraction_probe_1’ or ‘UserCase_Sample_device_width’) will arrive from the data entry of the user in the eLabFTW user interface (cf. Fig. 5, D).

Before moving on, it is important to note two important interoperability limits of eLabFTW. The first one is the possibility to group the ‘extra_fields’. Unfortunately, eLabFTW only allows one order of groups. In other words, one can create groups of the ‘extra_fields’, but one cannot create groups of groups. This is the main reason why we did not maintain the structure suggested by CHADA and turned it into a flat list of keys. The

⁷The code developed for this API integration is available in the GitHub repository of the thesis (see the end of the thesis for the link).

second – and probably most important – interoperability limit of eLabFTW is the fixed JSON Schema used to set up the ‘extra_fields’. Indeed, one cannot put one’s own JSON Schema in the software, as it will not be parsed properly by eLabFTW. One must use the structure specified in the documentation. This structure is a limit in that often interoperability derives from the use of common machine-actionable metadata schemas.

Despite the limitations, eLabFTW gives the possibility to host in a digitized and organized way all the records produced in a laboratory (or set of laboratories), making them findable (there is a local unique ID for every experiment, experiment template, and resource), accessible (eLabFTW is installed in a server), and reusable, at least locally. If one uses a controlled vocabulary or standard to build the ‘extra_fields’, it may even make the metadata interoperable (at least locally). Thus, this ELN is a valid and useful tool for FAIRification. In the next section, we will see how to go from the local to the global.

4.2.3 Step 3: Achieving Interoperability with NOMAD

Recall where we were in our pipeline. We have an experiment in eLabFTW. Attached to the experiment, a JSON contains all the relevant metadata, which we would like to publish in a FAIR way in NOMAD, the domain-specific archive and repository for materials science data (described in §3.3.3). How can this be done? The link between eLabFTW and NOMAD is not straightforward, it is rarely explored, and it is being discussed right now within the materials science community. One option is to export the experiment in eLabFTW with the ‘eln’ file format, a novel file format that enables the exchange of ELN entries and data (The ELN Consortium, 2022), and upload it on NOMAD. However, NOMAD is not able to parse and normalize the ‘extra_fields’, which are basically treated as raw data. Thus, this route does not deploy all the interoperability opportunities of NOMAD.

Therefore, as we already mentioned in §3.3.3, to achieve interoperability we deployed the NOMAD Metainfo. In other words, we have to make our metadata ‘speak’ with NOMAD. To do that, we envisioned a matching process between the keys of the flat conceptual metadata schema (i.e., the keys used in our eLabFTW JSON metadata) and the terms of the NOMAD Metainfo (cf. Fig. 5, Step 3a). At the moment the process is manual – but in the future, it may be automatized. Unfortunately, for most of the keys, there is no match – we should wait until NOMAD becomes populated enough with experiments and measurements like the SOT. However, for some keys there is a match – for example with regard to the structure of the sample, which is a thin film composed of several layers of

different substances. In this way, we reached a partial match of our JSON metadata keys with the terms of the NOMAD Metainfo.

Successively, we defined a NOMAD custom schema, in order to upload the metadata in NOMAD in a way which is at least partially interoperable (cf. Fig. 5, Step 3b). Now, let us have a look at a relevant portion of our custom schema, written in YAML.

```
definitions:
  name: SOT
  sections:
    SampleStructure:
      base_sections:
        - nomad.datamodel.metainfo.basesections.CompositeSystem
        - nomad.datamodel.data.EntryData
      m_annotations:
        eln:
          hide: ['datetime']
      quantities:
        UserCase_Sample_device_width:
          type: np.float64
          unit: mm
        m_annotations:
          eln:
            component: NumberEditQuantity
            display:
              unit: mm
      sub_sections:
        layers:
          section:
            quantities:
              layer:
                type: Substance
            m_annotations:
              eln:
                component: ReferenceEditQuantity
          repeats: true

    SOTMeasurement:
      base_sections:
        - nomad.datamodel.metainfo.eln.ElnBaseSection
        - nomad.datamodel.data.EntryData
        - nomad.datamodel.metainfo.basesections.CompositeSystemReference
      quantities:
        UserCase_Sample_sample_name:
          type: str
          m_annotations:
            eln:
              component: StringEditQuantity
        Experiment_RunNumber:
          type: int
          m_annotations:
            eln:
              component: NumberEditQuantity

    Substance:
      base_sections:
        - nomad.datamodel.metainfo.eln.Substance
        - nomad.datamodel.data.EntryData
      m_annotations:
        eln:
          hide: ['datetime']
```

```

quantities:
  UserCase_Sample_layer_thickness:
    type: np.float64
    unit: nm
    m_annotations:
      eln:
        component: NumberEditQuantity
        display:
          unit: nm

```

This is a YAML schema package with three section definitions: SampleStructure, SOTMeasurement and Substance. Let us start with the most basic one: Substance. The Substance here denotes one layer of the thin film (which is the structure of the sample). The definition of Substance has two base sections. One is EntryData, which, as mentioned in §3.3, only entails that what we are defining is a section to enter data. The other one is ‘Substance’. In this way, the section definition inherits the properties of the base section ‘Substance’ – such as the elemental composition. We may think of the relationship between our definition and the base section as an “is_a” relationship. However, we decide not to inherit (‘hide’ in the schema) the property ‘datetime’, for metadata quality reasons, namely, to avoid inconsistent values with other sections. To the definition of Substance, we added a property – or, in the NOMAD language, ‘quantity’ – namely the ‘UserCase_Sample_layer_thickness’. This term comes from the flat conceptual metadata schema and refers to the thickness of one of the layers of the sample.

Another definition in our schema is SampleStructure. The SampleStructures denotes the thin film. The SampleStructure inherits the properties of a CompositeSystem. Moreover, we had a repeatable set of quantities, the layers. But this quantity actually refers to the Substance we discussed above. In this way, we are able to model the structure of the sample with the NOMAD Metainfo: The ‘Substance’ is part of the ‘CompositeSystem’ (in the real world: the layers compose the thin film). Therefore, we describe the sample in an interoperable way. Since thin films are a kind of sample that is frequently used in materials science, an object of future research may be to write a schema package for thin films to be merged with the Metainfo. A ‘quantity’ is associated with this section definition, namely ‘UserCase_Sample_device_width’. This term too comes from the flat conceptual metadata schema, and it refers to the width of the thin film. This ‘quantity’ is a float (‘np.float64’) and it is expressed in millimetres (‘unit: mm’).

The last definition of our schema package is the ‘SOTMeasurement’. This section aims to represent an ELN entry for the SOT measurement. Indeed, one of the base sections defines a basic ELN entry (‘ElnBaseSection’), while another gives the possibility of

referencing a CompositeSystem. We defined another quantity, which refers to the name of the sample ('UserCase_Sample_sample_name'). This quantity, as well as 'Experiment_RunNumber', is an example of many other quantities that do not have a matching with the NOMAD Metainfo. Such quantities, taken from the flat conceptual metadata schema, may be added to the 'SOTMeasurement' definition.

We now have a customized specific schema. How can this customization bring about interoperability? Thanks to normalizers, which can read the base sections used in a specific custom schema, NOMAD automatically copies some of the uploaded data into a 'results' section, which is created for every entry. Thus, while the overall 'data' section contains the highly detailed data organized as the user wants, the 'results' section contains a copy of some of the data deemed most important. In Figure 7, we can see a screenshot of the 'data' sections of a NOMAD entry. The entry refers to a substance, silicon, and NOMAD is able to retrieve automatically many relevant information such as CAS URI, CAS number, elemental compositions, and many others – just from the name of the entry.

QUANTITIES	
substance name	Silicon
UserCase Sample layer thickness	<input type="checkbox"/> Unit nm
datetime	12/02/2025 10:30
substance ID	
CAS uri	substance/pt/7440213
CAS number	7440-21-3

QUANTITIES	
element	Si
atomic fraction	1
mass fraction	1

Figure 7: 'Data' section of a NOMAD entry

Such automatic retrieval is possible because of the 'Substance' base section. However, in the customized schema, I added one new quantity, 'UserCase_Sample_layer_thickness'. Since this quantity does not belong to the Metainfo, it does not appear in the 'results' section, in Figure 8, which however contains relevant information on the chemical formula of silicon (within the section 'material').

Figure 8: 'Results' section of a NOMAD entry

To conclude our pipeline, we have to upload into NOMAD the information coming from eLabFTW. For example, if in eLabFTW we have, as a portion of our metadata JSON file, “UserCase_Sample_sample_name”: “A9/B5”, we would like to have a NOMAD entry in which in the field “UserCase_Sample_sample_name” it is written “A9/B5” in an automatic way. To achieve that, we use a combination of the eLabFTW and NOMAD API in a Python code⁸. First, we GET the experiment from eLabFTW. Then, we isolate the target metadata from the experiment. Then, we create a folder with the YAML custom schema shown above. Then we hard code in Python several dictionaries that follow the structure of NOMAD entries. For example, for the measurement entry, we have: `{“data”: {“m_def”: “../upload/raw/SOT.schema.archive.yaml#/definitions/section_definitions/1”}}`. Successively, we edit this Python dictionary with the values coming from the experiment metadata. We can edit the dictionary with all the relevant key-value pairs coming from the JSON from eLabFTW. Recall however that the keys must be described as quantities of the ‘SOTMeasurement’ in our YAML schema. While developing this part, we ensure metadata quality. Namely, we transform the strings containing numbers in integers or floats, and we modify the date format from the Python datetime object to the ISO 8601 format (International Organization for Standardization, 2019), accepted by NOMAD.

We repeat the same process for every layer of the thin film, for the sample structure and for the entry of the measurement. Finally, we turn these Python dictionaries into JSON files, we put them in the same folder, zip the folder and upload it to NOMAD through the

⁸ Some of the code to do this was adopted from the GitHub repository Tools for Data Management and Curation (2024).

API.⁹ In this way NOMAD automatically reads the files as entries.¹⁰ Then, one can manually create references within the entries, for example, by referencing the various ‘Substance’ entries (representing the layers of the thin film) to the entry of the ‘SampleStructure’ (representing the thin film itself). Finally, we can publish our upload, and NOMAD will automatically assign a DOI to the output.

In summary, we conclude the pipeline by reaching partial interoperability, describing our experiment, when possible, with the NOMAD Metainfo. In our case, we successfully described the sample structure. It may be the case that other experiments can achieve partial interoperability in other ways. Finally, we retrieved information from eLabFTW and uploaded it into NOMAD.

⁹ The code developed to perform this API integration is available in the GitHub repository of the thesis (see the end of the thesis for the link). The code contains an advanced proof of concept, transferring all the relevant key-value pairs from the experiment in eLabFTW to NOMAD (approximately half of the metadata were transferred). The key-value pairs that were not transferred are other ‘quantities’ in the ‘SOTMeasurement’ definition and the logic behind the process is the same.

¹⁰ It may be the case that NOMAD parses a ‘Substance’ entry but does not automatically recognise the name of some substances. If it happens, one should manually add the elements to the entry of that substance to ensure interoperability. (In our case, we had to manually add the elements of the substance entry ‘CoFeB’).

Chapter 5

Discussion and Conclusions

This thesis described an exploratory FAIRification project for an experiment in the field of materials science, the SOT measurement. In Chapter 2, the necessary background was explained, in Chapter 3 we described the method and the tools used, and in Chapter 4 we illustrated the main result of the FAIRification. In sum, in our pipeline we made the CHADA metadata standard machine-actionable and gathered metadata thanks to an API integration between the computational environment of the laboratory and our favoured ELN, eLabFTW. The user's entry also contributed to the metadata. Finally, we uploaded the metadata into NOMAD by designing a custom schema using the NOMAD Metainfo and thus reaching partial interoperability. In this way, the metadata is ready to be published in NOMAD. In conclusion, the metadata are transformed from an unstructured, non-FAIR, format to an organized and (partially) FAIR format.

It is important here to highlight one limitation of this pipeline, due to the fragmented landscape of FAIRification in experimental materials science. In particular, as we mentioned in chapter 2, at the moment the experimental materials science community does not have a clear direction when it comes to FAIR data management. This is reflected in our pipeline, which is actually commanded by two bosses, i.e., CHADA and NOMAD Metainfo. Ideally, it should be the case that the CHADA has its own representation in the NOMAD Metainfo. Or vice versa, that the CHADA is written in a way which is compatible with the NOMAD Metainfo. An object of future research may be to develop a NOMAD plugin to make the CHADA machine-actionable. In general, it would be desirable that the standards (in the broadest sense) that guide metadata gathering and publishing are unique across the pipeline. After the experience of this project, we can say that – when it comes to choosing among standards – it is always important to keep in mind the *purpose* of FAIRification, which is, usually, enabling the reuse of scientific data. Ideally, then, if one *must* choose among many different standards, the choice should be towards the one that enables more reusability of one's own data. Indeed, in our project, even though we considered CHADA as a starting point, NOMAD was the arrival point of our pipeline. Generally, the risk is that the proliferation of standards may hinder the digitization and interoperability of data in the materials science community, leaving their potential untapped.

Despite this limitation, it is also important to acknowledge that our project showed the high potential of ELNs when it comes to FAIRification, especially with regard to metadata. In general, ELNs enable the digitization of information that was previously stored on paper. In our case, we customised our ELN so that it can take part in the FAIRification project. In the future, it would be great if ELNs could exploit their FAIRification potential and be more integrated with FAIR ecosystems, for example allowing the gathering of metadata with many different schemas or being compatible with ontologies. NOMAD, also functioning as an ELN, goes in this direction, but it has the shortcoming of not being very user-friendly.

To that end, an idea for further research may be to develop a user interface that automatizes further the metadata pipeline we envisioned, maybe integrating automatically eLabFTW and NOMAD. Another idea for further research would be to find a way to integrate the NOMAD Metainfo with the current ontologies of materials science, maybe using one of the foundational ontologies available (such as Basic Formal Ontology). Furthermore, our FAIRification project used the SOT measurement as a case study. However, we may adapt this pipeline to other experiments in materials science. In short, in the future it would be interesting to apply cutting-edge semantic technology to new scientific fields for the purposes of FAIR data management and, consequently, scientific discovery, explanation, and progress.

Code Availability

The code developed for this thesis is available at the following link:

<https://github.com/filippo-vasone/FAIR-metadata-pipeline-for-experimental-matsci>.

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